

ACHIEVING THE 2030 ENERGY EFFICIENCY TARGETS IN GEORGIA: IMPLEMENTATION AND KEY CHALLENGES

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Abstract

The signing of the Association Agreement between Georgia and the European Union in 2014, along with Georgia's accession to the Energy Community Secretariat in 2017, has driven significant reforms in the country's energy sector, including the development of energy efficiency policies and alignment with EU energy legislation. Energy efficiency is essential for sustainable development, reducing energy consumption, costs, and environmental impacts. The Law on Energy Efficiency and the Law on Energy Efficiency in Buildings establish regulatory measures and ambitious targets to strengthen energy performance across sectors. Within this process, Georgia has committed to achieving specific energy targets by 2030, as outlined in its National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) of Georgia. In terms of energy efficiency, a key objective is to limit primary energy consumption to 5.45 million tonnes of oil equivalent and final energy consumption to 5 million tonnes of oil equivalent. This article examines the progress towards these energy efficiency targets in Georgia and analyzes the main implementation challenges.

Keywords: Georgia, Energy Efficiency Targets, Energy Policy, NECP, Energy Community Secretariat, Decarbonization, GHG Emission, Energy Saving.

1. Introduction:

The signing of the Association Agreement between Georgia and the European Union in 2014, which fully entered into force in 2016, along with Georgia's accession to the Energy Community Secretariat in 2017, has driven a series of reforms and commitments in the country's energy sector. These commitments include the establishment of an attractive and stable energy investment environment, the promotion and adoption of energy efficiency as a sectoral priority, the introduction of energy-efficient technologies across various sectors, support for the development of renewable energy sources, the advancement of common-interest energy infrastructure, and the creation of a competitive, transparent, and efficient energy market in Georgia, gradually aligning the country with EU energy legislation.

Through close cooperation with the Energy Community Secretariat, Georgia has, since 2019, adopted energy legislation harmonized with the EU's Third Energy Package, including:

- **the Law on Energy and Water Supply;**
- **the Law on Energy Efficiency;**
- **the Law on Energy Performance of Buildings;**
- **the Law on Promotion of Electricity Production from Renewable Energy Sources;**
- **the Law on Energy Labelling.**

In 2024, Georgia also adopted its State Energy Policy and its annex, the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), which sets out the country's long-term energy strategy, priorities, and measures, including specific targets for 2030. Based on the 2022 Ministerial Council decisions of the Energy Community, Georgia, along with eight other member states, has established energy targets to be achieved by 2030. For instance, the share of renewable energy in final energy consumption is expected to reach 27.4% (from 19.85% in 2024, and approximately 75% in electricity generation). Additionally, Georgia must reduce greenhouse gas emissions from 39,460 tCO₂-equivalent in 1990 to 17,070 tCO₂-equivalent by 2030, representing a 47% reduction.

Of particular relevance for this study are the energy efficiency targets, which aim to limit primary energy consumption to 5.45 million tonnes of oil equivalent (from 5.1 million tonnes in 2021) and final energy consumption to 5 million tonnes of oil equivalent (from 4.7 million tonnes in 2021). These targets emphasize reducing energy losses and improving the efficiency of energy delivery to end-users.

Given that this dissertation focuses specifically on achieving energy efficiency targets, it will be pertinent in the first colloquium to discuss the achievements and challenges in this area at the regional level. The analysis will primarily rely on monographs, academic articles, annual progress reports by the Energy Community

Secretariat, and international expert assessments of regional outcomes.

It can be asserted that the achievement of any ambitious target is possible only if it forms part of a state-declared and officially endorsed policy. Notably, in 2019, the Energy Community Ministerial Council issued a decision making it mandatory for Georgia to adopt its State Energy Policy and its annex, the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), which was subsequently reflected in Georgia's Law on Energy and Water Supply. The development of this document began in 2019. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, energy consumption in 2020 was significantly lower compared to previous years. This was primarily because many enterprises temporarily closed or switched to fully remote operations, and fuel consumption declined due to transportation restrictions, among other factors. As a result, Georgia's energy balance during the pandemic deviated from traditional patterns, showing a downward trend. Consequently, the base years for modeling in the NECP were selected as 2016–2019, a period of steadily increasing energy consumption. This methodological choice results in projections and statistical data that differ from the current situation.

The process of developing Georgia's State Energy Policy and its annex, the NECP, took approximately five years. The Parliament approved the document on 27 June 2024, representing a significant step toward achieving the 2030 energy targets. It is noteworthy that no comparable policy-level document previously existed in the energy sector, making its parliamentary approval an unprecedented milestone. The NECP defines five key strategic directions aligned with the principal components established by the EU and the Energy Community Secretariat:

- **Decarbonization (renewable energy and greenhouse gas reduction)**
- **Energy efficiency**
- **Energy security**
- **Internal energy market**
- **Research, innovation, and competitiveness (NECP, 2024)**

The overarching objective of Georgia's State Energy Policy is to strengthen national energy security in both the short and long term, ensuring the reliable and uninterrupted delivery of diverse, high-quality energy to all consumers at fair prices.

The NECP provides a comprehensive analysis of the current state of the country's energy system, including existing, ongoing, and planned energy infrastructure, as well as the main strategic directions of Georgia's energy and climate policy. It presents multiple energy scenarios for achieving the defined targets, each representing an economically optimal combination of alternative technologies and measures based on assumptions and constraints. These scenarios assess the feasibility of reaching the stated objectives within the modeled limitations. According to the NECP, the primary conclusions and evaluations are projected up to 2030, while the scenarios extend projections to 2050.

2. Current Status of Energy Efficiency and Practical Actions for Achieving Target Indicators

Energy efficiency is a global challenge whose importance is increasing due to energy shortages, rising resource prices, high dependence on energy imports, and environmental concerns. In Georgia, approximately 80% of energy is imported, making energy efficiency a crucial tool for reducing import dependence and enhancing energy security.

Over the past decade, energy efficiency has received growing attention in Georgia. As noted earlier, its significance was further reinforced by the 2014 EU Association Agreement, which established recommendations and directives for energy efficiency. The European Union emphasizes the direct benefits of energy efficiency for the population; studies show that implementing energy efficiency measures in buildings—accounting for more than 30% of the country's total energy consumption—reduces utility costs, improves quality of life, and positively impacts health, the environment, and working conditions. Accordingly, achieving target indicators and minimizing energy losses requires the deployment of resource-efficient technologies across public, residential, industrial, and transport sectors.

The Law on Energy Efficiency, adopted in 2020, and the Law on Energy Performance of Buildings, updated in 2024 to reflect relevant directives, laid the foundation for energy audits, building certification, and heating and cooling system inspections. These regulations enable citizens to monitor their energy consumption, reduce utility costs, and make their homes more energy-efficient.

The introduction of a building energy performance certification scheme and minimum energy efficiency standards entails the development, approval, and practical implementation of the relevant methodology and subordinate legal acts. Annually, at least 1% of buildings under the administration of public authorities will be upgraded to meet the minimum energy efficiency requirements for the building or its components. This will include measures such as thermal insulation of schools and other public buildings, installation of energy-efficient lighting, and modernization or replacement of solid-fuel heating systems.

To ensure effective energy service provision, energy auditing, and the energy management of enterprises and buildings, training programs will be established to prepare qualified specialists, including the development of qualification and certification schemes.

The state will also promote energy-efficient procurement practices in the public sector, incorporating life-cycle costs, including energy expenditures, into public procurement processes. These measures are expected to strengthen the market for energy-efficient devices and demonstrate the state's leadership in the efficient use of energy (NECP, 2024).

Together with other technical activities, these measures are designed to achieve significant progress in energy consumption efficiency among Energy Community member states. While legislative harmonization represents an important milestone, actual progress largely depends on the quality and intensity of the implementation of practical measures.

3. Brief Analysis of Regional and International Experience and Practices

Georgia's political and economic security and its prospects for stable development are closely linked to the support of the international community. To strengthen energy security and advance Euro-Atlantic integration, Georgia actively develops cooperation with regional and Energy Community member states, based on partnership relations and in accordance with European energy legislation, the Energy Charter, and international best practices. Georgia's accession to the Energy Community has entailed concrete commitments to align its energy legislation with the European Union.

The Energy Community is an international organization that facilitates cooperation between the EU and its member states to achieve energy security, energy sustainability, and environmental objectives. It is noteworthy that Georgia is the only country in the region that holds full membership in the Energy Community while also possessing EU candidate status.

This process is accompanied by certain challenges. Notably, Georgia lacks direct physical interconnections with eight other member states, which creates additional barriers in the transposition and subsequent implementation of various regulations and directives. In total, the Energy Community has nine contracting parties: Georgia, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, and Ukraine. The European Union is also a contracting party to the Energy Community Treaty and serves as the organization's permanent vice-president.

Accordingly, when examining the achievement of national energy efficiency targets, it is important to consider the pace, accuracy, and challenges of directive

transposition in the above-mentioned countries. Studying these cases allows for a comparative analysis with Georgia and enables an assessment of both the degree of legislative alignment and the effectiveness of implementation.

➤ Georgia: 2030 Energy Efficiency Targets and Measures

Georgia's energy efficiency targets for 2030, as defined in the adopted and approved National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), align with the Energy Community's 2030 framework, including specific obligations under Directive 2012/27/EU (EED).

The Energy Community's current annual progress report highlights significant legislative progress, particularly in June 2024, when amendments to the Energy Efficiency Law and the Law on Energy Performance of Buildings were adopted. Within the following two years, over 20 secondary legal acts were issued under these laws, some of which are already being implemented.

For example, mandatory energy audits for Category I enterprises will be conducted once every four years, beginning in 2026. Simultaneously, work is ongoing on building energy performance certifications as well as inspection rules and procedures for heating and cooling systems.

Considering these measures, Georgia has the potential to approach its primary and final energy consumption targets by 2030. Figure N-3 presents Georgia's primary and final energy consumption targets for 2030 and the progress made in the energy efficiency sector (Energy Community Annual Implementation Report, 2025).

Figure N-1 – Primary and Final Energy Consumption Targets for Georgia and Progress in Energy Efficiency

Georgia has also demonstrated significant progress in the planning and deployment of renewable energy. As noted, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) has been submitted to the Government Administration for further consideration and is expected to be approved this year. The NECP was approved in 2024, and relevant regulations have already been aligned with the existing legislative framework by both regulators and

the Ministry. The construction of new generation facilities, as well as the increase in hybrid and electric vehicles in the transport sector, significantly contributes to raising the share of renewables in overall energy consumption.

Based on the above, the Energy Community's defined renewable energy targets and the current performance in Georgia are as follows:

Figure N-1.1 – Renewable energy target for Georgia and progress in the renewables sector

4. Implementation Challenges and Barriers

Despite significant legislative progress, as noted above, with both the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) successfully transposed into national legislation,

critical challenges remain. Key barriers to the development of energy efficiency in Georgia include insufficient data; low consumer awareness and motivation; limited knowledge of energy management and energy auditing; the unpreparedness of academic institutions and their curricula; and weak practices in the adoption

of new technologies and innovation. Additionally, there is a lack of knowledge on energy-efficient procurement among municipalities and state agencies.

There is a need to develop and implement methodologies for cost-benefit and regulatory impact assessments, to accredit training programs for energy auditors, and to establish certification mechanisms. Adequate state funding and institutional support represent significant obstacles, which, under constrained budgetary conditions, must be supplemented by external donor assistance and low-interest loans from international financial institutions (NECP, 2024). As per the Energy Community Annual Implementation Report, 2025, Georgia has the following status and progress of EE implementation:

Raising awareness, motivation, and professional qualifications in the industrial and construction sectors is essential for the effective implementation of both mandatory and voluntary measures. Another major barrier is the prevalence of subsidized tariffs in Georgia; relatively low electricity and gas prices, compared to the EU and regional countries, render many energy efficiency measures financially unviable and reduce incentives for efficient energy consumption.

5. Conclusion

To sum up, the above-mentioned information has been essential for analyzing Georgia’s position regarding the transposition of specific directives and regulations. The data indicate that, as an Energy Community member state, Georgia has achieved notable progress, although the overall performance remains moderate. While the implementation of energy efficiency measures still requires the development of a long-term strategy for building energy performance certification and the rehabilitation of existing buildings, certain milestones have already been established. In particular, the minimum energy efficiency requirements for new buildings, which came into force on 1 July 2023, and the creation of an Energy Savings Monitoring and Verification Platform (MVP) as mandatory transitional schemes, provide a foundation for setting more ambitious targets in the future.

The latest summary figure reflecting the 2025 annual progress of Energy Community member states is presented below:

Figure N-2 - Performance Indicators of Energy Community Member States

From the figure, it is evident that, compared to other countries, Georgia demonstrates an above-average performance. One of the main challenges for Georgia in achieving energy efficiency targets remains the absence of a dedicated implementing body (agency or fund). As the comparative analysis of other countries shows, several Energy Community member states effectively utilize the functions and responsibilities of such implementing institutions. Even Azerbaijan, which has no formal obligations regarding energy efficiency target achievement, has established a dedicated fund that operates effectively under the Ministry. Accordingly, it is reasonable to assume that Georgia could achieve even more substantial results with the establishment of a similar agency.

Finally, while significant legislative harmonization has been achieved under the framework of mandatory reforms, effective implementation requires systematic work and a timely transition from transitional measures to stable, coherent mechanisms that ensure continuous monitoring and updating of energy efficiency initiatives.

In conclusion, notable progress has been made in reducing both primary and final energy consumption. Future reductions in energy losses and increases in energy savings will largely depend on the state’s active

efforts to expand the share of resource-efficient technologies across the public, residential, transport, and industrial sectors, ultimately supporting the transition to a green energy economy.

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